

The Effect of Late-Night Screen Use on Children in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay: A Parent's Guide

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ABSTRACT

Late-night screen use is the practice of using electronic devices in the late evening or nighttime hours. It has become increasingly common for children around the world to engage in late-night use. Usage of late night screen can have positive effect including relaxation, educational opportunities and creativity on the child's development. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay. Study shows that children who use electronic devices before bedtime have poorer sleep quality and are more likely to suffer from depression, anxiety, fatigue and sleep disturbances. Parents should be aware of the potential risks of late night screen use on children. Therefore, parents should monitor their children's screen time and set boundaries on the amount of time spent using electronic devices and gadgets. This will ensure that the recommendations remain relevant and evidence-based. Advocate for policy changes: Work with local government agencies and policymakers to advocate for policies that promote healthy screen use habits among children. This may include regulations on advertising targeted towards children, limitations on screen time in public spaces, or guidelines for schools and childcare centers in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay. The purpose of the study is to provide parents practical and updated guide and strategies to help their children's screen time habits. The researcher used mixed methods- qualitative and quantitative design to have comprehensive understanding of the study.

Keywords: *Late-night screen use, Electronic devices, children, Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui, Albay, parents*

INTRODUCTION

We already live in a digital era. The rise of electronic devices and gadgets such as mobile phones, iPads, laptops, smartwatches, and the like is very common nowadays. They become an integral part of our daily lives, from communicating with our loved ones and playing games to simply searching for assignments and projects on educational sites to working remotely. It had made our lives convenient and efficient in every possible way.

Today, not only adults are using these gadgets, but they have also been introduced to children. It has become increasingly common for children around the world to engage in late-night use. One notable study was conducted by researchers at the (University of Glasgow, 2021) in Scotland, who analyzed data from more than 10,000 adolescents across Europe. The study found that those who reported more screen time, particularly in the evening, had poorer sleep quality and were more likely to experience symptoms of depression and anxiety. Another study conducted by (Eric Suni, 2023) of the National Sleep Foundation found that 90% of teenagers reported using electronic devices in the hour before bed, and those who did so were more likely to report feeling tired during the day and having difficulty concentrating in school. Adults should have at least seven hours of sleep. Moreso, children and teens need even more nightly sleep than adults (Melinda Smith, 2023). Sleep deprivation may be driven by voluntary choices that reduce available sleep time. For example, a person who decides to stay up late to binge-watch her favorite K-drama series may experience acute sleep deprivation. It is important to avoid things that can interfere with your sleep.

Late-night use refers to the practice of using electronic screens (such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, or televisions) during the late evening or nighttime hours, typically close to bedtime. It involves activities like browsing social media, playing video games, watching videos, or engaging in any screen-related activity (Kemp, 2020). Using such electronic devices can have a positive impact on a child's development including access to a wealth of resources, such as online courses. However, there are also potential risks, challenges, and adverse effects of the late use of screens at night. The use of gadgets and other electronic devices before bedtime can potentially have negative effects on various aspects of a person's well-being, including sleep, cognitive function, emotional health, and physical health (Elia Abi-Jaoude, 2020). The effect of late-night screen use on children and teenagers is a topic that has raised concerns among parents, researchers, and experts. Parents should not only monitor the duration of their children's use of their gadgets, but they should also be aware of the possible impact of late-night screen use on their children's well-being, especially in the physical and mental aspects. According to the report from (Samantha Murphy Kelly, 2021) of CNN Business, raising kids in this generation has become a challenge, but it is even harder for parents raising kids who are socially addicted to their gadgets and their social media accounts such as Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok. Therefore, understanding the risks and benefits associated with screen use can guide us in finding an appropriate balance and promoting healthier screen habits for our children.

As a parent in the Philippines, it is important to be aware of the potential risks of late-night screen use and take steps to manage your child's screen time (Amy Morin, 2020). This can include setting limits on screen time, encouraging physical activity and outdoor play, and promoting healthy sleep habits. By taking a proactive approach to managing screen time, parents can help ensure the health and well-being of their children.

A recent study has shown that Filipinos have the highest average screen time spent on phones and rank consistently high for average screen times on computers, social media, and gaming. The Philippines has almost 70 million smartphone users. Even though China has nearly a billion people, its average screen time only sits at 19.54% (Purnell, 2023). The Philippine government launched several campaigns to promote digital literacy and responsible screen use among youths and children.

The impact of late-night screen use on children and teenagers in barangays in the Philippines is similar to that of the wider population. In Albay province, particularly in Brgy. At Centro Oriental in the Municipality of Polangui, late-night screen use among children and teenagers is also a growing concern. Therefore, community-based initiatives can also play a vital role in promoting responsible screen use among young people. This can include organizing activities and events that encourage physical activity and social interaction, as well as providing resources and information on the risks of excessive screen time.

The topic of the impact of late-night screen use on children and teenagers is very timely, especially in the current era where electronic devices are ubiquitous and easily accessible. With the COVID-19 pandemic forcing many schools to shift to online learning and many people working from home, screen time has increased significantly for both adults and children. Additionally, the rise of social media and online gaming has led to concerns about the impact of excessive screen time on social and emotional development and the academic performance of children. Parents are increasingly seeking guidance on how to manage their child's screen time and promote responsible screen use.

This study aims to provide parents with an up-to-date guide on the impacts of late-night screen use as well as practical strategies to help them ensure a healthy and balanced approach to using the technology. It may also help them make informed decisions regarding their child's screen-time habits.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the children using excessive gadgets during night time in terms of:
 - Age;
 - Gender;
 - Family structure; and
 - Educational Attainment

2. What are the potential long-term effects of late-night screen use on cognitive function in children and teenagers in terms of:
 - Attention span;
 - Memory retention;
 - Brain development; and
 - Problem-solving skills

3. What is the relationship between late-night screen use and sleep patterns in children and teenagers in terms of:

- Sleep quality;
 - Daytime fatigue;
 - Sleep disturbances; and
 - Sleep duration
4. How can parents and caregivers effectively communicate the risks of excessive screen time to their children in terms of:
- Explaining the risks;
 - Leading by example;
 - Encouraging alternative activities; and
 - Monitoring screen time
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METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The research design for the Impact of Late-Night Screen Use: A Parent's Guide could be a mixed-methods design, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Qualitative and quantitative research design draw the strength with each other. (Georgia State University Library, 2023)

Quantitative research methods could be used to collect objective data on the frequency and duration of screen time, sleep patterns, and cognitive function, using tools such as surveys, sleep trackers, and cognitive tests (Saba Kheirinejad, 2023). This data could be analyzed using statistical methods to identify patterns and relationships between variables. Qualitative research methods could be used to collect subjective data on the experiences and perspectives of children and parents regarding late-night screen use, using tools such as interviews or focus group discussion. This data could be analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns in the data. (Anthony J. Onwuegbuzie, 2009)

By using a mixed-methods approach, the study can provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of late-night screen use on children and teenagers, incorporating both objective and subjective data and allowing for a more nuanced analysis of the issue.

2.2 Respondents

The subject of this research is the population of Barangay Centro Oriental in Polangui, Albay Philippines who were under the following category:

1. Parents when the research was conducted to gather information on their attitudes towards screen time, their management of their children's screen time, and their observations of the impact of late-night screen use on their children.
2. Children (2 years old up to 18 years old) to gather on their screen time habits, sleep patterns and cognitive function.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

RESPONDENTS (BARANGAY)	POPULATION (PARENTS)	POPULATION (CHILDREN 18 YEARS AND BELOW)
Centro Oriental	716	478

According to the updated projected mid-year population for the Philippines based on the 2015 POPCEN result, Polangui, Albay has forty four (44) barangays with a projected 96,169 population in 2022. The subject of this study will be one of forty four barangays in Polangui, Albay which is the Brgy. Centro Oriental. This barangay is divided into six (6) sub-barangays. According to the Barangay Health Workers (BHW), who were responsible for the data needed, there were a total population of 1,992 when the research was conducted. The researcher used a simple random sampling technique to select forty (40) parents and twenty-five (25) potential teens and children, which were considered representative of the total population for the whole period.

2.3 Research Instrument

Two survey questionnaires were prepared; one was administered to the parents affected by the late night screen use of their children and the other was conducted on the children itself. The parent's questionnaire was designed in English, Filipino, and Bicolano dialects to communicate with their children easily and vice versa. The questionnaire includes questions regarding the socio-demographics of the respondents- both parents and their children in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay (age, gender, family structure and educational attainment); potential long-term effects of late night screen use on cognitive function in children (attention span, memory retention, brain development and problem-solving skills); relationship between late night screen use and sleep patterns in children (sleep quality, daytime fatigue, sleep disturbances and sleep duration); and effective communication between parents and children of risk of excessive screen time (explaining the risks, leading by example, encouraging alternative activities and monitoring the screen time).

The questionnaires were developed based on the studies and literature of notable psychologists, including (Twenge, 2018) and (Shalini Paruthi, 2016). Both experiences are five-point Likert-type scales, ranging from "strongly disagree" (=1) to "strongly agree" (=5) that can be numerically coded for the quantitative data followed by one or two openended questions for the qualitative data collection.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The Barangay Health Workers (BHW), some of the parents and children in Brgy. Centro Oriental were consulted by the researcher regarding the study's conduct. After the permission was granted, the researcher secured consent before the interview. It was explained that the respondents were given autonomy to participate and answer the questionnaire and can cancel their participation if they decided to. It was also guaranteed that the respondents' data and responses were treated with confidentiality and were subjected to the provisions iterated in the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act 10173), overseen by the National Privacy Commission. This act ensures the protection of personal data and privacy of individuals. Compliance with this act is a crucial aspect of the research to safeguard the privacy and rights of the respondents.

After explaining the study and obtaining informed consent from parents and/or assent from participants, it will be divided into two groups: those who spend less than 5 hours per day while the other would consist of participants who used gadgets more than 5 hours a day.

2.5. Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed the data collected from the targeted respondents with the help of Microsoft Excel. As the result of the analysis of the interviews, the researcher has found positive and negative effects of late night screen time use of children as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Percentage Distribution

Category	Frequency	% distribution
Agree	21	32.31%
Strongly Agree	38	58.46%
Neutral	1	1.54%
Disagree	2	3.08%
Strongly Disagree	3	4.62%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Profile of the Parents and Children affected by the Late-Night Screen Use

Table 3. Parent's Profile

NAME OF THE PARENT	DATE OF BIRTH	AGE IN YEARS AND MONTHS	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT
Parent 1	3/20/59	64	COLLEGE UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 2	1/2/97	26	COLLEGE GRADUATE
Parent 3	9/20/97	26	COLLEGE GRADUATE
Parent 4	9/22/69	54	COLLEGE GRADUATE
Parent 5	6/28/75	48	ELEMENTARY GRADUATE
Parent 6	3/23/73	50	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 7	9/19/71	52	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 8	2/4/47	75	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 9	5/19/78	45	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 10	12/9/39	83	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 11	3/12/82	41	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 12	11/2/57	65	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 13	1/4/67	56	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 14	4/7/87	36	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 15	10/15/90	33	VOCATIONAL
Parent 16	6/16/96	27	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 17	6/16/73	50	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 18	9/25/65	58	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 19	10/26/61	62	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 20	8/17/64	59	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 21	7/8/69	54	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 22	6/9/59	64	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 23	11/24/62	61	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 24	1/29/66	57	VOCATIONAL

Parent 25	5/10/99	24	VOCATIONAL
Parent 26	10/28/96	26	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 27	11/4/51	72	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 28	9/17/63	60	ELEMENTARY GRADUATE
Parent 29	10/7/63	60	ELEMENTARY GRADUATE
Parent 30	12/26/36	87	ELEMENTARY UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 31	2/9/64	59	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 32	1/15/69	54	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 33	10/25/95	27	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 34	3/12/92	31	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 35	5/24/98	25	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 36	12/6/52	70	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 37	2/10/46	77	ELEMENTARY GRADUATE
Parent 38	10/7/39	83	HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATE
Parent 39	3/20/75	48	ELEMENTARY UNDERGRADUATE
Parent 40	4/12/74	49	HIGH SCHOOL UNDERGRADUATE

As shown in Table 3, those forty (40) parents were grouped into 3 (three) categories: age of the household members, gender and their educational attainment. There were 45% male parents and 55% female parents. The oldest individual being 64 years old and the youngest being 26 years old. There were 3 parents who were College Graduates (8.11%), 1 parent who didn't finished his Bachelor's Degree (2.70%), 4 parents were Elementary Graduates (10.81%), 2 parents also didn't finished their primary education (5.41%); There were 18 parents who were high school graduates (48.65%) and there were 9 who didn't finished their secondary education (24.32%).

Table 4. Personal Data of Parents affected by Late-Night Screen Use in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui, Albay

Personal Data (Parents)	No.	%
Age		
26-35	9	22.5%
36-47	3	7.5%
48-59	14	35%
60-71	8	20%
72-83	5	12.5%
84-95	1	2.5%
Gender		
Male	18	45%

Female	22	55%
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Undergrad	2	5.41%
Elementary Graduate	4	10.81%
High School Undergrad	9	24.32%
High School Graduate	18	48.65%
College Undergrad	1	2.70%
College Graduate	3	8.11%

Table 5. Children's Profile

NAME OF THE CHILDREN	DATE OF BIRTH	AGE IN YEARS AND MONTHS	EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT
Child 1	9/14/08	15	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 2	4/30/10	13	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 3	8/27/11	12	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 4	2/17/13	10	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 5	4/7/14	9	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 6	10/21/15	7	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 7	10/24/08	14	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 8	4/29/08	15	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 9	11/6/10	12	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 10	5/8/12	11	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 11	2/7/14	9	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 12	12/15/13	9	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 13	11/29/07	15	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 14	10/16/08	14	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 15	5/7/12	11	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 16	1/18/06	17	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 17	12/28/08	14	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 18	7/21/13	10	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 19	2/2/10	13	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT
Child 20	11/24/14	8	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 21	6/5/05	18	COLLEGE STUDENT
Child 22	7/26/15	8	ELEMENTARY STUDENT
Child 23	12/20/21	3	PRE SCHOOL
Child 24	8/20/05	18	SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL
Child 25	12/7/08	15	HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT

As shown in Table 5, those twenty-five (25) children respondents were grouped into 3 (three) categories: name of the children, age and their educational attainment. There were 56% male children and 44% female children. The oldest individual being 18 years old and the youngest being 5 years old. There were one (1) college student (4%), eleven (11) elementary students (44%), nine (9) high school students (36%), three (3) senior high school students (12%) and one (1) preschool student (4%).

Table 6. Personal Data of Children on the Late-Night Screen Use in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui, Albay

Personal Data (Parents)	No.	%
Age		
0-4	1	4%
5-9	6	24%
10-14	11	44%
15-18	7	28%
Gender		
Male	14	56%
Female	11	44%
Educational Attainment		
Preschool Student	1	4%
Elementary Student	11	44%
High School Student	9	36%
Senior High School Student	3	12%
College Student	1	4%

Table 7. Screen use pattern and effect among the children of Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui, Albay

Screen Use	No.	%
Devices used on a daily basis		
Phone	8	32%
Tablet	10	40%
Laptop	2	8%
TV	5	20%
Amount of screen time used on a daily basis		
<1 hour	2	8%
1-2 hours	8	32%
3-5 hours	14	56%
6 -8 hours	1	4%
>8 hours	0	0%
Amount of screen time spent before going to sleep		
20 minutes or less	4	16%
21-40 minutes	18	72%
41-60 minutes	2	8%
>60 minutes	1	4%
Using devices at bedtime affect your productivity on the next day?		
Yes	20	80%
No	3	12%

Maybe	2	8%
If yes, what is the effect?		
Daytime Fatigue	12	48%
Sleepiness (quality, disturbances and duration)	8	32%
Low concentration at school	4	16%
Headache	1	4%

The most used devices were Tablet (40%), Phone (32%) and TV (20%). Children mostly used their gadgets/ screens for 3-5 hours on a daily basis (56%) and 1-2 hours (32%). As for time spent using devices before sleep while lying in bed, 18 children (72%) reported that they used 21-40 minutes of screen time before going to bed, 4 children (16%) used 20 minutes or less screen time before going to sleep, 2 children (8%) used 41-60 minutes and 1 children (4%) spent most of his/her time using gadgets for more than an hour. A total of 20 (80%) told that using devices at bedtime affects their productivity on the next day. The most reported effect was feeling fatigue (48%), followed by sleepiness (32%), low concentration at school (16%), and headache(4%).

3.2 Positive effects of Late Night Screen Use in Children

Late-night screen use in children, which includes activities such as watching television, playing video games, or using smartphones and computers, has become increasingly common in today's digital age. While excessive screen time and late-night usage can have negative effects on children's health and wellbeing, it is important to acknowledge that there can also be some positive outcomes associated with this behavior. Following are five positive effects of late night screen use in Children:

- **Educational Opportunities.** Late-night screen use can provide access to educational resources and platforms that allow children to learn and explore various subjects of interest. Online tutorials, educational websites, and interactive apps can offer engaging ways for children to acquire knowledge.
- **Creativity and Inspiration.** Late-night screen use may provide children with exposure to creative content such as movies, documentaries, music, or artwork. This exposure can inspire imagination, encourage creativity, and spur a child's interest in artistic pursuits.
- **Relaxation and Entertainment.** Like adults, children also use screen time as a means of relaxation and entertainment. Engaging in activities like watching a movie or playing video games before bed can help some children wind down, alleviate stress, and promote a sense of enjoyment and relaxation.
- **Connection and Communication.** Late-night screen use, particularly for older children and teenagers, can allow for social connection and communication with friends and family. Through online platforms, children can stay in touch, share experiences, and develop relationships, even when physical distance is a barrier.

However, it's important to note that moderation and appropriate parental guidance are crucial. Excessive late-night screen use can still disrupt sleep patterns, hinder cognitive development, and negatively impact physical health. Therefore, it is advisable to set limits on screen time and ensure a healthy balance between offline and online activities.

3.3 Negative effects of Late Night Screen Use in Children

In today's digital age, screen devices have become an integral part of many children's lives. Parents sometimes used screen time as a reward but also believed digital technology would have a negative impact on their child's behavior, social skills, sleep, and physical activity. However, excessive screen time, especially late at night, can have detrimental effects on their health and well-being. The blue light emitted by screens and the stimulating nature of digital content can impede sleep, disrupt circadian rhythms, and affect the overall quality of rest. Additionally, prolonged late-night screen use can lead to reduced physical activity, poor academic performance, impaired social interactions, and an increased risk of developing behavioral and mental health problems. It is essential for parents and caregivers to understand the negative consequences of late-night screen use in children and take appropriate measures to establish healthy screen habits and promote optimal child development.

- **Sleep Disruptions.** The blue light emitted by screens can interfere with the production of melatonin, a hormone that regulates sleep. Late-night screen use can disrupt a child's sleep patterns, making it harder for them to fall asleep and leading to sleep deprivation. This can affect their overall health, mood, cognitive functioning, and academic performance.

- **Poor Sleep Quality.** Even if a child manages to fall asleep, late-night screen use can lead to poor sleep quality. The stimulating content, fast-paced games, or engaging social media interactions can make it difficult for children to fully relax and enter a deep, restorative sleep. This can result in daytime drowsiness, difficulty concentrating, and decreased cognitive functioning.
 - **Negative Impact on Mental Health.** Excessive screen use, especially late at night, has been linked to an increased risk of mental health issues in children. It can contribute to feelings of anxiety, depression, loneliness, and low self-esteem. The content they are exposed to, such as violent or inappropriate material, can also have a negative impact on their emotional well-being.
 - **Impaired Academic Performance.** Lack of quality sleep and daytime drowsiness due to late-night screen use can impair a child's cognitive abilities, attention span, and memory, which can negatively affect their academic performance. It can lead to difficulties in concentrating, retaining information, and problem-solving.
 - **Physical Health Issues.** Late-night screen use often replaces physical activities and outdoor play, leading to a sedentary lifestyle and an increased risk of obesity and related health issues. Spending excessive time on screens can contribute to poor posture, eyestrain, and musculoskeletal problems such as neck and back pain. To promote a healthy lifestyle, it is important to establish screen time limits, encourage nighttime routines that do not involve screens, and create tech-free zones in bedrooms to ensure children get adequate sleep and maintain their overall well-being.
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DISCUSSION

Technology's usage has both positive and negative effects on young children. It can offer educational benefits, such as helping toddlers learn new skills and it can also stimulate activities for curiosity and creativity. It can be beneficial for the parents to keep their children occupied while they attend to other tasks. However, parents should strive to balance using technology as a tool for learning and entertainment while prioritizing other forms of knowledge and playtime for their children.

Figure 1. Brgy Centro Oriental Total Population as seen on the Brgy. Hall's Secretary Office

Conclusions

Excessive screen media usage in children can have both positive and negative impacts on their development. Regarding cognitive development, screens have the potential to enhance education and learning. However, several studies have shown that excessive screen time can have detrimental effect on your child's socio-emotional development including blurred vision, sleep disturbances, fatigue, reduced mood and emotional well-being and many more. Language development is also affected by screen time, as it diminishes the quantity and quality of interactions between children and caregivers. Contextual factors such as co-viewing and appropriateness of content play a role in determining the impact on language development.

Parents also play a crucial role in managing and reducing screen time by raising awareness, setting boundaries, and providing behavioral controls. Parents should also set as an example by managing their own screen time. Overall, it is important, not only for the parents but for caregivers, educators, and healthcare professionals as well to understand the potential risks of excessive screen usage and implement strategies to promote healthy development in children. Minimizing late-night screen use among children is vital for their overall well-being and development. By promoting healthy sleep habits and setting boundaries, we can ensure that children have a balanced relationship with technology while safeguarding their physical and mental health.

The main goal of this study was to determine the effects of late night screen time to children. Overall, this study supports the notion that there is a significant relationship between children before the age of 2 years and high frequency of screen time especially before bedtime. Future research is necessary to if there is a causal link between screen time and children's sleep.

Recommendations

This guide aims to equip parents in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay with practical strategies to navigate the challenges associated with late-night screen use. By implementing these recommendations, parents can help their children establish a healthy balance between technology and other essential aspects of their lives.

It is important to note that these recommendations are not meant to demonize screens or technology. Instead, they aim to empower parents to make informed decisions and create an environment that supports their child's overall well-being.

To effectively address the impact of late-night screen use, it requires a collaborative effort from parents, educators, community organizations, and policymakers. By working together, we can create a healthier digital landscape for children in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay. Here are the researcher's recommendation:

1. Establish clear screen time boundaries: Create and enforce specific rules around when and how much screen time is allowed for children in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay. This can include setting limits on the duration and timing of late-night screen use.
2. Encourage alternative activities: Encourage children to engage in alternative activities that do not involve screens, especially during late-night hours. This can include reading books, engaging in creative pursuits, or participating in physical activities.
3. Create a screen-free bedtime routine: Establish a consistent routine that promotes relaxation and quality sleep. This can involve avoiding screens at least one hour before bedtime, engaging in calming activities such as reading or storytelling, and creating a peaceful sleep environment.
4. Educate parents about the potential risks: Provide parents in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay with information about the potential negative effects of late-night screen use on children. This education can help parents understand the importance of setting boundaries and prioritizing healthy sleep habits.
5. Foster open communication with children: Encourage parents to have open and honest conversations with their children about the impacts of excessive screen use, including late-night screen time. This dialogue can help children understand the reasons behind the rules

and develop a sense of responsibility for their own well-being.

6. Promote healthy lifestyle habits: Emphasize the importance of a balanced and healthy lifestyle for children. Encourage parents to prioritize physical activity, outdoor play, and social interactions to counteract the sedentary nature of screen time.

7. Provide resources and support: Offer parents in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay access to educational materials, workshops, or support groups that focus on managing screen time and promoting healthy habits for their children. This can empower parents with the tools and knowledge they need to make informed decisions.

8. Collaborate with schools and community organizations: Partner with local schools and community organizations to implement awareness campaigns or workshops aimed at educating parents, children, and educators about the effects of late-night screen use. This collaborative effort can enhance the impact and reach of the parent's guide recommendations.

9. Continuously evaluate and update the guide: Regularly assess the effectiveness of the parent's guide and update it based on emerging research and feedback from parents in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay. This will ensure that the recommendations remain relevant and evidence-based.

10. Advocate for policy changes: Work with local government agencies and policymakers to advocate for policies that promote healthy screen use habits among children. This may include regulations on advertising targeted towards children, limitations on screen time in public spaces, or guidelines for schools and childcare centers in Brgy. Centro Oriental Polangui Albay.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ensuring the highest ethical standards in this research is of paramount importance. To address ethical considerations comprehensively, the study will undergo a rigorous ethical review by an Institutional Ethics Evaluation Committee. This committee will be tasked with evaluating the research from an ethical perspective, identifying potential ethical issues, and ensuring that all ethical principles and guidelines are strictly adhered to throughout the research process. Several critical ethical factors will be taken into account to uphold the integrity and ethical soundness of this study. These ethical considerations include:

Autonomy and Informed Consent. Respect for the autonomy of research participants is fundamental. The research will prioritize obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring that they fully understand the research objectives, procedures, potential risks, and their rights as participants. The voluntary nature of participation will be emphasized, and participants will have the option to withdraw from the study at any point without repercussions.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Protecting the privacy and confidentiality of participants is a core ethical principle. All collected data, including personal information and responses, will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Identifying information will be anonymized or pseudonymized to prevent the disclosure of participants' identities.

Beneficence. The research will aim to maximize benefits and minimize harm to participants and stakeholders. This includes ensuring that the research outcomes contribute positively to the understanding of the topic and avoiding any harm or adverse consequences to participants.

Non-Maleficence. The principle of non-maleficence obliges researchers to do no harm. Every effort will be made to conduct the research in a manner that avoids physical, psychological, or emotional harm to participants. Ethical safeguards will be in place to protect the well-being of all involved.

Testing for Plagiarism. Plagiarism, a breach of academic integrity, will be vigilantly monitored and prevented throughout the research process. Proper citation and acknowledgment of sources will be strictly adhered to, and plagiarism detection tools may be employed to ensure the originality of the research work

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